

Impact of TV Viewing on Academic Performance of High School Students Aged 16-18 in Islamabad: A Survey Study (2024-2025)

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study was to explore the influence of television viewing on the academic performance of high school students. A sample of 100 students, comprising 50 boys and 50 girls, was selected using a stratified sampling method from two high schools in Islamabad. The study aimed to categorize students as either heavy or light television viewers based on their responses to a questionnaire. This questionnaire inquired about the amount of time spent watching television and the types of programs watched. The relationship between television viewing habits and academic performance was then analyzed by comparing the academic achievements of both groups. The results indicated that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of heavy and light television viewers. Whether students spent a considerable amount of time watching television or only a small amount did not seem to affect their academic results. This suggests that television viewing, in isolation, may not be a determining factor in academic success. Furthermore, the study found that other external factors, such as study habits, parental involvement, and socioeconomic background, could play a more substantial role in influencing students' academic performance. Thus, the research emphasizes the need to consider multiple variables when examining the academic success of students, rather than attributing their performance solely to their television-watching habits. In conclusion, while television viewing remains a popular activity among students, it does not appear to have a significant impact on academic achievement, suggesting that other factors may have a more direct influence on student performance.

Keywords: Television Viewing, Academic Performance, High School Students, Heavy vs. Light Viewers, Stratified Sampling

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